

HISTORIOGRAPHY OF THE POLICY OF ECONOMIC ZONING IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY OF THE SOVIET STATE OF THE SECOND HALF OF THE 20TH CENTURY

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Abstract. *The work of the Soviet authorities on the restoration of the country's economy in the years after World War II, the policy of economic zoning in the national republics, the base of regulatory documents on it and the Greater Central Asian economic region and its peculiarities form the main issues of research. This article covered the historiography of the policy of economic zoning in the national economy of the Soviet state of the second half of the 20th century.*

Keywords: *economic zoning, economic zones, national archives of Uzbekistan, literature, research, works published abroad, articles published in Soviet times and years of independence.*

INTRODUCTION

In the current globalized conditions, each state sets its own goals, focusing on free economic zones, which are considered the foci of investments. In the world experience, more than 4 thousand free economic zones operate today, close to each other, but with different names. They were established to perform various tasks during their career. Economic zones in turn consist of Free Trade and R & D areas, production export areas, special areas (offshore centers, reclamation areas, eco-economic areas and tourist areas).

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

The policy of economic zoning of the Soviet state in Uzbekistan was carried out on the example of the Tashkent economic region on the basis of periodic and problem principles. In this case, literature, studies published during the Soviet period, independence years, as well as works published abroad, articles were studied, commented on, critically analyzed and summarized.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used the principle of historicity and techniques such as systemicity, analysis, comparative-chronological, sequence, objectivity.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Before the beginning of the Second World War, the study of the policy of the Soviet government on the management of the economy, which set the tasks of “strengthening” the material and technical base of communism and “increasing” the standard of living of the working people, is important in its relevance.

Archival sources on the topic point out that the Central Asian republics, in particular the Tajik SSR, the Turkmen SSR, the Kyrgyz SSR, the Uzbek SSR, due to their superiority over other regions in terms of production potential, natural resources, labor, were called the Central Asian economic region by uniting these republics, while at the same time being able to provide the country's interests with sufficient The Greater Central Asia Economic Zone was under the control of the planning and Coordination Council.

The foundation of the National Agricultural Council of the Uzbek SSR, which is held in the National Archives of Uzbekistan-R.2384, foundation of the Council of people's economy of the Central Asian economic region (Sredazsovnarkhozstroy) - R.2433, the foundation of the planning and Coordination Council of the Council of the national economy of the Central Asian economic region - R.2303, foundation of the Department of energy and the Soviet of national economy of the National Economy Council of the Tashkent economic region-R. 2137 and other funds stored a huge amount of information on the industrial, agricultural life of economic districts. At the moment, it should be noted that the information in these funds dates back to the 1960s, and includes precisely the periods associated with the activities of the councils of the national economy. These funds kept information about existing industrial enterprises in the economic regions, which in the literature of the Soviet period provide information about a huge number of specific problems about the production of industrial enterprises, which were raised to the Blues and praised.

For example, in the fund of the Council of people's economy of the Central Asian economic region (Средазсовнархозстрой. R-2433) records show that the cotton grown in the economic regions under the Central Asian Economic Council was of very poor quality and was shipped to yengil industries in this wet, dirty state. This naturally led to an increase in spending costs. For example, 88.2 percent of the 1962 crop was Cotton handed over in such a wet and dirty state, resulting in 7 million for the raw materials handed over. the ruble paid little. This was the case in a large number of cotton ginning plants under the National Board of Agriculture of the Central Asian economic region. They did not carry out cotton cleaning, drying, etc., on time or on demand. More than two thousand protest petitions on the quality of cotton were received from textile factories all over the country in the 6th month of 1962. In terms of fiber production, Samarkand cotton mill produced 737 tons of cotton, injection cotton mill 491 tons of cotton, Unicorn cotton mill 738 tons of cotton overused.

There have also been articles published in a number of timed press pages on the subject, which can witness the economic zoning policy being extolled and praised in all respects to the Blues. These articles describe that "the widespread advance in the construction of communism requires an increasingly consistent positioning of the industry, which ensures the saving of social Labor, the complex development of districts and the specialization of their economy". The economic regions praised the "consistent implementation of the national policy of the Communist Party during the years of Soviet power, making radical revolution changes in the field of Economics and culture."

A number of thematic literature has also been published, which can be studied in four groups. The first group includes works created in the years of the reign-years of the Soviet state, the second group includes works created in the independence-years, and the third group includes works created abroad on the topic.

The works included in the first group were written under the influence of their ideas on communist ideology, but they are distinguished by their richness in various sources. The "evolving" deviations from the path that the Soviet people's economy Party had initiated have been researched by various sources. At the moment, these works can also be studied as works on Soviet national economy, as well as precisely on the issues of economic zoning. According to the literature written during the reign-years of the Soviet state, the industrialization of Uzbekistan played a huge role in the development of the Republican National Economy, the reconstruction of

cities and villages on a socialist basis and the development of the culture and material well-being of the Uzbek people.

A number of authors who studied exactly the policy of economic zoning of the Soviet state consisted of the sum of specialized territorial production complexes of the country's economic-administrative regions – individual provinces, territories, Allied and autanom republics or a group of small provinces. In economic regions economic turnover, the product considered necessary for the national economy of the country, natural resources were obtained without much expenditure, relying on cheap labor.

“Совершенствование структуры народного хозяйства Узбекской ССР” in the title book, The authors analyze the division of Uzbekistan into 6 economic regions according to regional specialization and give detailed information about the characteristics of each economic region. In the monograph” progressive shifts in the structure of the Uzbek industry”, the Uzbek SSR is divided into five economic regions. The book is divided into Tashkent, Fergana, Zarafshan, (south-west), Lower Amudarya, Surkhandarya, (South) economic districts. According to the author of the work, these economic regions included the following regions of the Republic: Tashkent raion-Tashkent and Syrdarya regions; Fergana raion-Fergana, Andijan and Namangan Oblast-rini; Zarafshan raion-Samarkand, Bukhara region and Karakalpakstan ASSRni, southern raion - Surkhandarya region.

In the monograph published by the employees of the Institute of economics of the Academy of Sciences of the Uzbek SSR, the economic regions are divided into seven. In particular, Tashkent (Tashkent region), Jizzakh-Syrdarya (Jizzakh, Syrdarya regions), Fergana (Fergana, Andijan, Namangan regions), Samarkand-Karshi (Samarkand, Kashkadarya regions), Bukhara-Navoi regions (Bukhara, Navoi regions), lower Amudarya (Karakalpakstan ASSR and Khorezm regions), as well as Surkhandarya region alone will be divided into Surkhandarya economic region. Also, in addition to these economic regions, the authors also divide the regions within the Republic into a complex of territorial production. Among them are the rayon complexes of Fergana (1954), lower amudarya (1959-1960 and 1974-1977), Bukhara-Kyzylkum (1972), Angren-Olmalik (1964-1967), the production complex of the mountain industry. At the moment, the authors divide the developed complexes of the Fergana territorial complex and the Angren-Olmalik mountain industry into the earliest and most advanced territorial production complexes in the Republic.

In general, in many literature, the number of economic raions is given differently, but in all of them the features of economic raions, their place in the country's national economy are indicated. In our opinion, it is possible to know that the use of reserves to the extent possible in Soviet economic policy is considered the first issue to be resolved. The Sarab, ultimately unthinkable, scientifically unproven ideas, such as the maximum use of opportunities, the assimilation of states in the capitalist system, put the economic regions of the entire country, as well as the economy of the Uzbek SSR, in a much more complex situation. “Since these economic regions were directed to one area of the national economy (raw materials), various food and industrial goods were brought to the territory mainly from abroad, meeting 50% of the needs of the Republic”.

The country, in particular, studied the division of Uzbekistan into economic regions. While analyzing the natural conditions of Uzbekistan, Bedrinsev noted that “Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, is located in the southernmost latitudes in the USSR and far from the open seas, and is the place from the temperate region to the subtropical region. This geographical situation also

affects the climate of Uzbekistan, its climate is continental, that is, the temperature varies greatly, in summer the temperature is very high, there is little moisture in the air, and precipitation is very low. Some of Uzbekistan's raions, which are hundreds of kilometers apart, differ in climate somewhat".

There are also a number of other works about the economic regions of the country, which state that each economic region should have a main link, that is, one or more economic sectors that are of Union importance and are developed with the aim of satisfying the needs of the entire socialist society, each economic region should also have a complex economic one, which developed.

V.M. Kostennikov wrote that according to the decree of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR of May 10, 1957, the whole country was divided into 104 economic raions. Of these, 68 were in the Russian Federation, 11 in the Ukrainian SSR, 9 in the Kazakh SSR, 5 in the Uzbek SSR, and the rest of the economic raions consisted of one per Republic. He noted that the republic, territory, autonomous regions within the country are united into a separate economic region, depending on their economic development, or a single economic region, consisting of several republics, regions, depending on their low development. Thus the 15 allied republics in the whole country were divided into 8 provinces. The RSFSR, depending on the different national composition, economic and natural state, as of January 1, 1958, combined in its composition 14 autanom Republics, 7 autanom regions, 49 Regions, 6 regions, 10 national districts.

N.N. In kolosovsky's case, Kazakhstan is divided into four raions, including the Northern one, which specializes in agriculture, mainly sowing wheat and growing meat; the southern one – planting wheat, sugar, rice, cotton and other technical crops; the Western one – oil and salt-rich lands, which the author also divides into four cycles. The first "23" cycles are industrialized-agrarian steppe lands, the "24" cycle is a developed area of coal, ferrous metallurgy, hydropower, the "25" cycle is Hydro –hydropower, chemical, specialized in non – ferrous metal mining, the "26" cycle is – the Turkestan SSR, which is part of the Central Asian economic region, consisting of developed areas of oil and gas production, the complex hydropower and hydromelioration complex of the Tajik SSR, the Kyrgyz SSR, the Uzbek SSR, specialises in oil and gas production, mining industry, metallurgy, cotton, rice, fruit and vegetable production in the valleys, and wheat is grown in Mountain and mountainous regions. This divides the raions into cycles, and introduces into it the sphere of petroenergochemistry, hydroeneogomeliorative, industrialized - agrarian region, as well as non-ferrous metallurgy, petroenergetics of the main type of Rayon.

Economist N.S. Ziyodullayev writes that economic management in this direction "divided the national economy into sectors and managed it on the basis of planning, eliminating the fragmentation of the socialist national economy." The author noted that the natural conditions of Uzbekistan are diverse and mainly favorable for the development of various sectors of the national economy. By the 1960s, the republic ranked fourth in terms of population among the former allied republics after the RSFSR, Ukraine, and Kazakhstan, and was the first among the four republics of the Central Asian Economic Region. Specialization in the field of cotton production of the Uzbek SSR also affected the industrial structure of the republic, and in this case, the production of mineral fertilizers, cotton cleaning, textile industry, enterprises supplying machines and equipment for this industry, the development of agricultural machinery, and the production of cotton raw materials, which included a large regional agricultural complex, were organized.

However, this is such a major expansion in the national economy and specialization in one area strengthened the planning policy in the country and practically strengthened economic monopolism. Situations alien to Soviet society, such as policies, market relations, free practice of money and Commodity Exchange, carried out without regard to the Basic Laws of economic development, were also reflected in the economy. The social and economic and financial aspects of the unified macroeconomic system of the USSR did not correspond to national interests.

It should be noted that a number of articles related to the period under study have also been published. These articles were more devoted to the Soviet economy, which received much praise, raising the economy of socialist society to the Blues.

With the independence of Uzbekistan, thanks to the opportunities created in the field of history, it was possible to study the development of the industry of Uzbekistan by historians, in particular, the real state of the economic situation in the Republican regions, scientifically analyzed by sources. It should be noted that these books provide brief information about the role of light industry in the economy of the Republic during the Soviet period. In Particular, D. Bobojonova notes that the policy of doubling economic regions has created demographic difficulties in the regions, a complex situation in the provision of housing, food, while the Republic has the necessary resource opportunities. According to the author, “the placement of light industrial enterprises in the Republic was carried out without planning, like other industrial enterprises. For example, at the beginning of the 1980s, 60 percent of the entire volume of products fell on the cities of Tashkent and Samarkand, 27 percent on the cities of Andijan, Bukhara, Namangan, Kokand, while there was not a single sewing enterprise in Jizzakh and Termez”.

CONCLUSION

The fundamental work “history of Uzbekistan (1917-1991)”, which took an important place in the coverage of the topic, took an important place. The book details Uzbekistan’s life in the era of contradictory processes in the socio-economic life of the country, stating that the book “despite some positive shifts in the socio-economic development of the USSR, in general, in the mid-60s of the 20th century, when the economy was under the negative influence of the Soviet model of administrative-administrative, negative situations in the economy are cited, such as the fact that the methods of development and economic stimulation of industry and the development of productive forces do not meet the limits of modern requirements.

X.Yunusova interprets the 80s of the 20th century, noting the fact that the country is based on territorial production of the national economy, the role of Uzbekistan in it, showing its characteristic signs of unilateral, weak development of economic development of Uzbekistan, introducing the following into them. These are: firstly, in most of the existing industrial enterprises in the Republic, technological equipment was already outdated, in disrepair, 50% of labor processes were carried out manually, and secondly, the lack of qualified specialists in production, personnel landing, obstacles to independent conduct of personnel policy, neglect in the training of national workers and specialist personnel, failure to require responsibility and skill from, the unskilled use of material resources was a serious obstacle to the path of economic development, and, fourth, the lack of interest of workers and employees in their labor, the scarcity of monthly salaries, the inability to organize the work process, the lack of attention to quality and efficiency are highlighted in the issues of attitude to labor discipline.

Who conducted research on a matter close to the topic we chose. If Khaydarov, in his monograph on the role of the industry of Uzbekistan in the unified national economy complex,

described the structure of the national economy councils as “the fact that the offices of material and Technical Supply were crushed and centralized also caused many people not to participate in production, perfecting the structure of economic management, over-centralization of management and socialist planning describe the expansion of its organizational form in leadership of the economy, as a consequence of the emergence of many excessive costs, such as views from an irresponsible and narrow departmental point of view”.

I.Khaydarov, analyzing the issues of economic zoning in the Soviet Union, writes that in 1938-1940 the scheme of economic zoning of the USSR was developed anew, and they were transformed into 13 large economic regions. The economic regions include the center, the Northwest, Northern Europe, the Volga region, the North Caucasus and the Lower Don, the Urals, Western Siberia, Eastern Siberia, the Far East, the South (Ukrainian SSR and Moldavian SSR), the East (Byelorussian SSR, Azerbaijan SSR and Armenian SSR), Central Asia and Kazakhstan (Kazakh SSR, Uzbek SSR, Kyrgyz SSR, Tajik SSR and Turkmen SSR). The author concludes that the Economic – Administrative Region was considered a certain territorial part of the national economy, having not only economic unity, but also administrative unity. The author also analyzes the post-World War II state of economic zoning. However, not every economic region and its role is covered separately in the work.

In the articles of G. Yusupova, who studied the economic zoning policy of the Soviet state on the example of the Fergana economic region, analyzing the industry, agriculture, machine-building industry, and cocoon production of this region, the author emphasized that the Fergana economic region has its place not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the whole country.

Some aspects of the chosen topic have also been analyzed in foreign literature, covering in part the topics devoted to the history and spiritual life of the Allied republics, including Uzbekistan, socio-economic development, and their content and conclusions are sufficiently weighty and contradictory.

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